

ADVANCED TRAINING AS A DEVELOPMENT FACTOR OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATORS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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The article deals with actual issues of preschool educators' communicative competence in complementary professional education system (advanced training); conceptual and terminological mechanism is revealed as well.

В статье анализируются актуальные вопросы развития коммуникативной компетенции педагогов дошкольных образовательных учреждений в системе дополнительного профессионального образования (повышение квалификации), раскрывается понятийно- терминологический аппарат данной проблемы.

Key words: preschool education, communication, communicative competence, preschool educators' communicative competence, advanced training.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, коммуникация, коммуникативная компетентность, коммуникативная компетенция педагогов дошкольных образовательных учреждений, повышение квалификации.

The modern educational strategy focuses preschool teachers on the development of competencies demanded by modern practice. In order to create the necessary conditions for achieving modern quality of preschool education, it is necessary to develop technologies aimed at changing the internal position of the teacher, his value-semantic definition as a necessary condition for the adoption and development of new pedagogical ideas. The need to update and improve the quality of preschool education, the introduction of various models is inevitable it leads to the updating of the functionality of teachers of preschool educational institutions.

Defining the conditions that ensure the quality of preschool education, it is necessary to highlight the most important:

- the use of health-saving technologies that will allow the educational process to be organized in such a way that the child can develop without excessive physical and mental stress that undermines health;
- a high level of quality of educational programs and their methodological support, the content of which will allow teachers to build the educational process in accordance with modern requirements and levels of development of society;
- enrichment of the subject-developing environment, the filling of which will provide the child with an opportunity for self-development;
- a high level of communicative competence of the teacher, whose main function is to help the child adapt to life in the world around him, developing such significant abilities as the ability to know the world, act in the world, and show attitude to the world.

All the above positions are priorities in ensuring the quality of preschool education. At the same time, in our opinion, the implementation of each condition is impossible without the participation of a competent teacher, ensuring the organization of the successful development of a child in a pre-school educational institution. Competence as a unity of theoretical and practical readiness of a teacher to perform professional functions characterizes not only the activity, but also the teacher himself as its subject in his independent, responsible, proactive interaction with the world. Due to this property, competence integrates the professional and personal qualities of a teacher, directs them to mastering knowledge and purposeful application in forecasting, planning and implementation of activities, activates the teacher in the development of his own abilities, in the pursuit of self-realization in socially useful activities, ensures his professional development during the period of professional training (advanced training).

We use the terms "competence" and "competence" not as synonyms, but as concepts inextricably linked to each other, namely: the formation of competence is understood by us as the formation of a certain range of knowledge, skills that should be possessed, and competence acts as a result of the formation of certain knowledge and skills, something that a person already knows quite well.

In N.V. Kuzmina's research, groups of competencies that make up the professional competence of a teacher are identified, while considering a set of communicative competencies, the author clarifies that each of which is necessary to establish contact with pupils and their parents, to transfer their own pedagogical experience to other teachers [2].

Communicative competence was initially considered from a linguistic point of view as the ability to realize linguistic competence in various conditions of speech communication, taking into account social norms of behavior and communicative expediency of the statement. At the same time, the formation of communicative competence was assigned the role of the main and leading one in the process of teaching a foreign language. Its leading component is speech (communication) skills, which include the ability to speak, the ability to read with understanding, the ability to understand by ear and the ability to write.

From our point of view, communicative competence is a demonstrated area(s) of successful communicative activity based on learned means and strategies of verbal communication, supported by language skills and speech skills.

With all the variety of approaches to the study of the structure of communicative competence (M.Kanal and M.Svein, L.Bachman and A.Palmar, M. M.Vyatytutnev, V.A.Kokkota, N.I.Geiz, V.M.Topalova, etc.), its most common components are:

- linguistic (vocabulary, grammar, phonetics, spelling);
- discursive (construction of oral and written texts);
- pragmatic (successful achievement of a communicative goal);
- Strategic (overcoming communication difficulties);
- sociocultural (compliance with sociocultural norms).

The communicative competence of a teacher is a professionally significant, integrative quality, the main components of which are: emotional stability (associated with adaptability); extraversion (correlates with status and effective leadership); ability to design direct and feedback communication; speech skills; the ability to listen; the ability to reward; delicacy, the ability to make communication "smooth". From our point of view, communicative competence is, first of all, the personal quality of a teacher, formed in the process of personal development

and self-development; secondly, an indicator of the teacher's awareness of the goals, essence, structure, means, features of pedagogical communication; the level of proficiency in appropriate technology; individual psychological qualities of a specialist; striving for continuous improvement of communicative activity; orientation to the human personality as the main value, as well as the ability to non-standard, creative solution of problems arising in the process of pedagogical communication. Professional communication is the core of a teacher's communicative competence, it always implies community, similarity, mutual aspiration to understand and accept the other, not only to rationally measure and react, but also to empathize emotionally.

In this regard, in theory, as well as in the practice of preschool and additional vocational education, the issue of modern technologies for the development of communicative competence is one of the most undeveloped and time-consuming, which is explained by:

- firstly, the fact that in the history and development of preschool education on at various historical stages, various and often directly opposite methodological approaches and concepts of preschool children's development prevailed, and therefore to the professional competence of teachers;
- secondly, the idea of practitioners that the development of preschoolers should be based on the subject-information model of education in the same type of educational institutions;
- thirdly, at different levels of speech and communicative development of preschool children, which requires additional competencies of teachers working with this category of children.

The normative requirements for professional activity are reflected in the qualification characteristics of the teacher. Its structure includes basic knowledge, skills, and skills necessary and sufficient to operate successfully. It is obvious that in a dynamic, developing society it is impossible to achieve the required level of qualification once and for all.

This implies the need for professional development as a form of value-semantic, meaningful and technological enrichment of the professional activity system. The contradiction between the required and the real level of communicative competence of teachers is deepening in the reform of the preschool educational system in Uzbekistan. It is possible to resolve this contradiction if, in the conditions of the professional development system, a pedagogical technology for the development of the communicative competence of preschool education teachers is developed.

The analysis of the research by N.A.Koroleva, S. G. Molchanova, etc., allowed us to consider professional development as a system of organizational and pedagogical measures involving appropriate content, methods and means aimed at assisting in the increment of professional competence. The objectives of professional development are, first of all, the development of professional skills and culture, updating the theoretical and practical knowledge of preschool education specialists in accordance with modern requirements of a competence-based approach to the level of qualification and the need to master innovative methods of solving professional problems.

In the context of the development and improvement of the entire preschool system It becomes obvious that there is a need to revise many "traditional" approaches to learning problems, to find new ways to improve the quality of teacher training for working with preschool children, meeting the requirements of new social conditions of social development.

To this end, we have studied in detail the problem of developing the communicative competence of preschool teachers at the theoretical and methodological level and identified the historical aspects of the emergence of this problem and promising directions for its development. The analysis of socio-historical and theoretical-pedagogical prerequisites for the formation and development of the communicative competence of teachers of preschool education made it possible to create a solid basis for its practical use in the conditions of modern additional professional education.

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